

EFFECTS' OF NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020 ON FUTURE OF TEACHER EDUCATION OF INDIA

¹Somdyuti Rakshit, ²Prof. Jayanta Mete

¹Research Scholar, Department of Education, University of Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal- 741235, India

²Department of Education, Faculty of Education, University of Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal- 741235, India

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Abstract: A Teacher takes a hand, opens a mind and touches a heart. Teaching is the only profession where all three 'H' (Hand, Head, Heart) important equally. Teachers truly shape the future of our children and therefore, the future of our nation. Teaching is the profession that teaches all of the other professions. It is because of the noblest role that the teacher in India was the most respected member of society. Recently Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) under the Government of India published final report National Education Policy 2020 (NEP-2020). NEP-2020 divided teacher education in two parts, first one school education and second one is under higher education. NEP-2020 planned something new for teachers which help improvement of teacher education programme in India. This paper discusses the planning of new NEP-2020 for teachers in school education and higher education programme and also the implementation process.

Keywords: Teacher Education, National Education Policy, MHRD.

1. INTRODUCTION

A Teacher takes a hand, opens a mind and touches a heart. Teaching is the only profession where all three 'H' (Hand, Head, Heart) important equally. Teachers truly shape the future of our children and therefore, the future of our nation. Teaching is the profession that teaches all of the other professions. It is because of the noblest role that the teacher in India was the most respected member of society. Only the very best and most learned became teachers. Society gave teachers, or gurus, what they needed in order to pass on their knowledge, skills, and ethics optimally to students. Today, however, the status of the teacher has undoubtedly and unfortunately dropped. The quality of training, recruitment, deployment, service conditions, and empowerment of teachers is not where it should be, and consequently the quality and motivation of teachers does not reach the standards where it could be. The high respect for teachers and the high status of the teaching profession must be revived and restored for the very best to be inspired to enter the profession, for teachers to be well-motivated and empowered to innovate, and for education to therefore reach the heights and levels that are truly required to ensure the best possible future for our children and our nation.

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study helps to identify the future of teacher education programme after National Education Policy 2020 implemented in India both school level and higher level. This study helps to identify the how NEP 2020 should helps to improves the Indian education system in both school level and higher level. This study also shows how NEP 2020 should implement in Indian education system.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

3.1. Future of Teacher Education Programme in School Level.

3.2 Future of Teacher Education Programme in Higher Level.

4. TEACHER EDUCATION IN SCHOOL LEVEL

Recruitment and deployment:

- To ensure that truly excellent students enter the teaching profession - especially from rural areas - a large number of merit-based scholarships shall be instituted across the country for study at outstanding 4-year integrated B.Ed. programmes. In rural areas, special merit-based scholarships will be established that also include preferential employment in their local areas upon successful completion of their B.Ed. programmes. Such scholarships will provide local job opportunities to outstanding local students (especially female students), so that these students may serve as local-area role models and as highly-qualified teachers who speak the local language. Incentives will be provided for outstanding teachers to take teaching jobs in rural areas, especially in areas with the greatest current teacher shortages and greatest needs for outstanding teachers. A key incentive for teaching in rural schools will be the provision of local housing near or on the school premises.
- The harmful practice of excessive teacher transfers will be halted, to ensure that teachers can build relationships with and become invested in their communities, and so that students have continuity in their role models and educational environments. Transfers will occur in very special circumstances, e.g., to solve two body or other family-related issues, or for promotions of outstanding teachers and administrators to leadership positions, as suitably laid down in a Structured manner by State/UT governments.
- Teacher Eligibility Tests (TETs) will be strengthened to better test material correlated to being outstanding teachers, both in terms of content and pedagogy. The TETs will also be extended to cover teachers across all stages (Foundational, Preparatory, Middle and Secondary) of school education. For subject teachers, suitable TET test scores in the corresponding subjects will also be taken into account for recruitment. To gauge passion and motivation for teaching, a classroom demonstration or interview will become an integral part of teacher hiring at schools and school complexes; these interviews would also be used to assess comfort and proficiency in teaching in the local language, so that every school / school complex has at least some teachers who can converse with students in the local language.
- To ensure an adequate number of teachers across subjects - particularly in subjects such as art, physical education, vocational education, and languages - teachers could be hired to a school/school complex and sharing of teachers across schools can be considered in accordance with the grouping of schools format adopted by State/UT governments.
- To promote local knowledge and expertise, schools/school complexes will be permitted and indeed will be supported with suitable resources to hire local eminent persons or experts as 'specialised instructors' in various subjects, such as in traditional local arts, vocational crafts, entrepreneurship, agriculture, or any other subject where local expertise exists and would benefit students and help preserve and promote local knowledge.
- A comprehensive teacher-requirement planning exercise will be conducted across India and in each State to assess expected teacher and subject vacancies over the next two decades. All the above-described initiatives in recruitment and deployment will be scaled as needed over time, with the aim to fill all vacancies with outstanding teachers, including outstanding local teachers.

Service environment and culture:

- The primary goal of overhauling the service environments and cultures of schools will be to maximise the abilities of teachers to do their jobs effectively, and to ensure that they are part of vibrant, caring, and inclusive communities of teachers, students, parents, principals, and other supporting staff, all of whom share a common goal: to ensure that our children are learning.
- A very first requirement in this direction will be to ensure decent and pleasant service conditions at schools. Adequate and safe infrastructure, including working toilets, clean drinking water, clean and attractive spaces conducive to learning, electricity, computing devices, and internet, library and sports and recreational resources will be important to provide to all schools in order to ensure that teachers and students are comfortable and inspired to teach and learn in their schools.

- The State/UT Government may adopt innovative formats, such as school complexes, rationalization of schools, etc. for effective school governance. The creation of school complexes for example, could go a long way towards building vibrant teacher communities. The hiring of teachers to school complexes could automatically create relationships between schools across the school complex; it might also help ensure excellent subject distribution of teachers, creating a more vibrant teacher knowledge base. Teachers at very small schools may not remain isolated any longer and may become part of and work with larger school complex communities, sharing community best practices with each other and working collectively and collaboratively to ensure that all children in the system are learning. School complexes could also share counsellors, technical and repair staff etc to further support teachers and help create an effective community environment for learning.
- In collaboration with parents and other key local stakeholders, teachers will also be more involved in the governance of schools/ school complexes, including as members of School Management Committees/ School Complex Management Committees.
- To prevent the large amounts of time spent currently by teachers on non-teaching activities, teachers will not be engaged in work that is not directly related to teaching (except for rare events that do not interfere with their class work); in particular, teachers will not be involved in election work during non-election period, cooking of midday meals, and other strenuous administrative tasks, so that they may fully concentrate on their teaching-learning duties.
- To help ensure that schools have positive learning environments, the role expectations of principals and teachers will explicitly include developing a caring and inclusive culture at their schools, for more effective learning for all, and for the benefit of all in their communities.
- Teachers will be given more autonomy in choosing finer aspects of curriculum and pedagogy, so that they may teach in the manner that they find most effective for the students in their classrooms and communities. Teachers will be recognised for novel approaches to teaching that improve learning outcomes in their classrooms.

Continuous professional development:

- Teachers will be given constant opportunities for self-improvement and to learn the latest innovations and advances in their profession. To ensure that every teacher has the flexibility to optimise their own development as teachers, a modular approach to continuous teacher development will be adopted. Developmental opportunities, in the form of local, state, national, and international teaching and subject workshops, as well as online teacher development modules, will be available to all teachers so that each teacher may choose what is most useful for their own development. Platforms (especially online platforms) will be developed so that teachers may share ideas and best practices. Each teacher will be expected to participate in, say, 50 hours of CPD opportunities every year for their own professional development. Initially the focus of CPD should be on orienting all teachers towards competency based learning and related pedagogies, such as experiential learning, art and sport integrated approach, etc.
- Leaders such as school principals and school complex leaders will have similar modular leadership / management workshops and online development opportunities and platforms to continuously improve their own leadership and management skills, and so that they too may share best practices with each other. Such leaders will also be expected to participate in 50 total hours of CPD modules per year, covering leadership and management, as well as content and pedagogy for the teaching aspects of their jobs with focus on preparing and implementing pedagogical plans based on competency and outcome based education.

Career management and progression:

- Teachers doing outstanding work must be recognised, promoted, and given salary raises, to incentivise all teachers to do their best work. Therefore, a robust merit-based tenure-track, promotion, and salary structure will be developed, with multiple levels within each teacher rank that incentivises and recognises excellent and committed teachers through tenure, promotions, and salary increases. A system of multiple parameters for proper assessment of performance will be developed for the same by the State/UT Government based on peer reviews, attendance, commitment, hours of CPD, and other forms of service to the school and the community, etc. Such merit-based assessments would be used to determine tenure decisions and the rate of promotions and salary increases for each teacher.

- Vertical mobility of teachers based on merit will also be paramount; outstanding teachers with demonstrated leadership and management skills would be trained over time to take on academic leadership positions in schools, school complexes, and at BRCs, CRCs, BIETs, and DIETs.

Approach to teacher education:

- Recognising that the best teachers will require training in high-quality content as well as pedagogy, teacher education will gradually be moved into multidisciplinary colleges and universities. As colleges and universities all move towards becoming multidisciplinary, they will also aim to house outstanding education departments that offer B.Ed. and M.Ed. degrees.
- By 2030, the minimum degree qualification for teaching will be a 4-year liberal integrated B.Ed. degree that teaches a range of knowledge content and pedagogy, and includes strong practicum training in the form of student-teaching at local schools. The 2-year B.Ed. programmes will also be offered, by the same multidisciplinary institutions offering the 4-year integrated B.Ed., and will be intended only for those who have already obtained Bachelor's Degrees in other specialised subjects. These B.Ed. programmes may also be replaced by suitably adapted 1-year B.Ed. programmes, and will be offered only to those who have completed the equivalent of 4-year multidisciplinary Bachelor's Degrees or who have obtained a Master's degree in a specialty and wish to become a subject teacher in that specialty. All such B.Ed. degrees would be offered only by accredited multidisciplinary higher educational institutions offering 4-year integrated B.Ed. programmes.
- All B.Ed. programmes will include training in time-tested as well as the most recent techniques in pedagogy, including with respect to foundational literacy and numeracy, multilevel teaching and evaluation, teaching children with special needs, teaching children with special interests or talents, use of educational technology, and learner-centred and collaborative learning; all B.Ed. programmes will also include strong practicum training in the form of in-classroom teaching at local schools.
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- Special shorter local teacher education programmes will also be available at BIETs, DIETs, or at school complexes themselves, so that eminent local persons can be hired to teach at schools or school complexes as 'specialised instructors', for the purpose of promoting local knowledge and skills, e.g., local art, music, agriculture, business, sports, carpentry and other vocational crafts.
- Shorter post-B.Ed. certification courses will also be made widely available, at multidisciplinary colleges and universities, to teachers who may wish to move into more specialised areas of teaching, such as the teaching of students with special needs, or into leadership and management positions in the schooling system, or move from one stage to another between foundational, preparatory, middle and secondary stages.
- Finally, order to fully restore the integrity of the teacher education system, the thousands of substandard standalone Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) across the country will be shut down as soon as possible by the Higher Education Regulator.
- The NCF for Teacher education, 2009 (NCFTE 2009) outlines many excellent approaches that are still relevant for accomplishing effective teacher education. This document will be revisited and updated by NCTE by the end of 2021, taking into account the changing context of teacher education today and, in particular, all the above Policy points, and will be made available in all regional languages.

5. TEACHER EDUCATION IN HIGHER LEVEL:

- Teacher education is truly vital in creating the team of school teachers that will shape the next generation. Teacher preparation is an activity that requires multidisciplinary perspectives and knowledge, the formation of dispositions and values, and the development of practice under the best mentors. Teachers must be grounded in Indian values, languages, knowledge, ethos, and traditions, while also being well-versed in the latest advances in education and pedagogy.

- Heartbreakingly, the teacher education sector has been beleaguered with mediocrity as well as rampant corruption due to commercialisation. According to the Justice J S Verma Commission (2012) constituted by the Supreme Court, a majority of standalone teaching institutes over 10,000 in number - are not even attempting serious teacher education, but are essentially selling degrees for a price. Regulatory efforts so far have neither been able to curb the corruption rampant in the system, nor enforce basic standards for quality, and in fact have had the negative effect of curbing the growth of excellence and innovation in the sector. The sector and its regulatory system are therefore in urgent need of revitalisation through radical action, in order to raise standards and restore integrity, credibility, efficacy, and high quality to the teacher education system.
- In order to improve and reach the levels of integrity and credibility required to restore the prestige of the teaching profession and thereby attain a successful school system, substandard and dysfunctional teacher education institutions (TEI) that do not meet basic educational criteria must and will be shut down. This effort will be launched in a mission mode by MOE with strong political will, positive administrative intent, and an effective implementation strategy. All TEIs will be held accountable to adherence to the basic criteria for approval of their programmes; after giving one year for remedy, if any breaches are found, they will be shut down if the breaches are not remedied. There must be a sound legal approach developed to ensure this enforcement is carried out effectively. By 2023, India should have only educationally sound teacher preparation programmes in operation, developing professionally competent teachers.
- All independent TEIs will be required to convert to multidisciplinary institutions by 2030, since they will have to offer the 4-year integrated teacher preparation programme.
- The 4-year integrated B.Ed. offered by such multidisciplinary HEIs will, by 2030, become the minimal degree qualification for school teachers. By 2030, every HEI offering a teacher education programme will be multidisciplinary and offer the 4-year integrated B.Ed. programme.
- Multidisciplinary higher educational institutions will work towards establishing high-quality education departments and teacher education programmes, and will be strongly supported by government funding to achieve this goal. Such HEIs will ensure the availability of a range of experts in education and related disciplines as well as specialised subjects. Each higher educational institution will have a network of government and private schools and school complexes to work with in close proximity, where potential teachers will student-teach (among other synergistic activities between HEIs and school complexes, such as community service, adult and vocational education, etc.).
- Admission to pre-service teacher preparation programmes, like all HEI admissions, will be carried out in large part through subject and aptitude tests as conducted by the National Testing Agency.
- The faculty profile in Departments of Education will necessarily aim to be diverse. Not everyone would be required to have a Ph.D., but teaching experience and field research experience will be highly valued. Faculty with training in areas of social sciences that are directly relevant to school education (e.g., psychology, child development, linguistics, sociology, philosophy/political science) as well as from science education, mathematics education, social science education, and language education programmes will be attracted and retained in teacher education institutions, to strengthen multidisciplinary education of teachers and provide rigour in conceptual development.
- All fresh Ph.D. entrants, irrespective of discipline, will be required to have taken 8-credit courses in teaching / education / pedagogy related to their chosen Ph.D. subject during their doctoral training period. Exposure to pedagogic practices, designing curriculum, credible evaluation systems, and so on will be ensured, since many research scholars will go on to become faculty. Ph.D. students will also have a minimum number of hours of actual teaching experience gathered through teaching assistantships and other means. Ph.D. programmes at universities around the country must be re-oriented for this purpose. Opportunities for Ph.D. students to assist faculty as teaching assistants must be created as part of all Ph.D. programmes.

6. IMPLIMENTATION OF NEP 2020 IN SCHOOL AND HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM IN INDIA

Any policy is only as good as its implementation. Such implementation will require multiple initiatives and actions, which will have to be taken by multiple bodies in a synchronised and systematic manner. Therefore, the Policy outlines key actions to be led by various bodies (including MHRD, RSA, Union and State Governments, education-related Ministries, State Departments of Education, Boards, NTA, the regulatory bodies of school and higher education, NCERT, SCERTs, schools,

and HEIs) along with timelines and a plan for review, in order to ensure that the Policy is implemented in its spirit and intent, through coherence in planning and synergy across all these bodies involved in education.

Implementation will be guided by the following principles.

First, implementation of the spirit and intent of the Policy will be the most critical matter. While the Policy provides much detail, the intent and the spirit of the Policy must serve as the most important consideration.

Second, it is important to implement the policy initiatives in a phased manner, as each policy point has several steps, each of which requires the previous step to be implemented successfully.

Third, prioritisation will be important in ensuring optimal sequencing of policy points -and that the most critical and urgent actions are taken up first - thereby enabling a strong base.

Fourth, comprehensiveness in implementation will be key; as this Policy is interconnected and holistic, only a full-fledged implementation, and not a piecemeal one, will ensure that the desired objectives are achieved.

Fifth, since education is a concurrent subject, it will need careful planning, joint monitoring, and collaborative implementation between the Centre and States.

Sixth, timely infusion of requisite resources - human, infrastructural, and financial - at the Central and State levels will be key for the satisfactory execution of the Policy.

Finally, careful analysis and review of the linkages between multiple parallel implementation steps will be necessary in order to ensure effective dovetailing of all initiatives. This will also include early investment in some of the specific actions (such as the setting up of early childhood education infrastructure) that will be imperative to ensuring a strong base and a smooth progression for all subsequent programmes and actions.

7. CONCLUSION

Yearly joint reviews of the progress of implementation of the policy, in accordance with the targets set for each action, will be conducted by a designated team constituted by RSA and the corresponding State body. By 2030, it is expected that the past decade would have provided ample opportunities for evaluation, fine tuning as well as major changes, if called for, to be effected. Thereafter, a comprehensive review of the status of the implementation of the policy in its entirety will be undertaken. In the decade of 2030-40, the entire policy will be in an operational mode, following which another comprehensive review will be undertaken. It is, of course, expected that annual reviews will continue throughout. This NEP 2020 is excellent in plan, and we all know any policy will be good only when it implement properly. Now this is very challenging to implement this policy properly in India. If this policy implemented properly then the future of Indian education system (school and higher) will be changed drastically.

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